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The Ukrainian Press-Bureau of Diplomatic Mission of the Ukrainian People's Republic in Rome as a Lesson for Contemporary National Journalism

Mykola Tymoshyk,

Doctor of Philology, Professor

Kyiv National University
of Culture and Arts

Ye. Konovaltsia str., 36

01601, Kyiv, Ukraine

e-mail: nkin@ukr.net

ORCID ID 0000-0002-7011-3022

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The article is written on the basis of the library and archive collections of Ukrainian emigration in Rome, worked out by the author during the research internship in Italy. For the first time, the little-known page of Ukrainian-Italian relations is covered from the perspective of the rise, organization of work and the results of the activities of the Ukrainian Press Bureau of the UPR Diplomatic Mission in Rome in 1919–1920.

As it is known, from the beginning of the formation of the Ukrainian People's Republic, diplomatic missions from Kyiv were sent to several influential countries of Western Europe. Their main task was to widely inform the leaders of the Entente countries regarding the situation in Ukraine and the recognition of the Ukrainian People's Republic as a sovereign independent stateseeek from these countries. In terms of resolving the Russian-Ukrainian problem, this government adhered to the pro-Russian position at that time.

Given that the Italian government did not recognize Ukraine as an independent state, the UPR diplomatic mission had no official status and in fact worked in Rome under semi-legal conditions. The mission was headed by the son of the famous Ukrainian historian Dmytro Antonovych.

The characteristics of staff members of the mission such as Vsevolod Shebedev, Taisiia Lypovetska-Balmen, Ivan Grinenko, Antonio Peskalotzi, typists-machinists, Italians of origin, Sandrini and Bettanuri are represented.

The press activity of the mission and, in particular, the head of the press office Yevhen Onatsky, are analyzed in detail. The editorial policy of the "Bulletin of the Ukrainian Press Bureau in Rome" and the Italian weekly "La Voce del Ucraina" was analyzed.

The conclusions highlight the main results of the press and publishing activities of this bureau. And they were the following:

- issue of the "Bulletins of the Ukrainian Press Bureau in Rome" (an information publication published twice or three times a week in Italian in a volume of two to four pages, an edition from 100 to 300 copies; 56 numbers of this edition were saved) by cyclotyle method;*
- issue of the analytical periodical "Voice of Ukraine" (according to the plan, the weekly in Italian, 50 numbers appeared in the world);*
- preparation of publications for the Italian press by the bureau staff;*

- conducting lectures on Ukrainian studies for the Italian public;
- publication and distribution of brochures on socio-political subjects and books of classics of Ukrainian literature translated into Italian.

Key words: Ukraine, Italy, Press Bureau, UNR Diplomatic Mission, Dmytro Antonovych, Euhen Onatskii, bulletin, «La Voce dell'Ucraina» newspaper, relations between Ukraine and Italy, Italian press, Ukrainian issue in Europe

Topicality and novelty of the article are conditioned by the absence in scientific publications of at least minimal fact-based information on conditions and efficiency of the existence of Ukrainian published word in Italy in general and in the period of the activities of Ukrainian Press-Bureau of Diplomatic mission of Ukrainian People's Republic (UPR) in Rome during 1919–1920 in particular.

The aims of the article are:

- to characterize the preconditions of the existence of UPR diplomatic missions in European countries and Italy in particular;
- to ascertain the staff of workers and the working conditions of the Ukrainian press-bureau in Rome;
- to outline the main trends and results of the Mission activities;
- to give a retrospective review of the first Italian-language newspaper for Ukrainians «La Voce del'Ucraina».

Preconditions of the outset of the activities

The emersion of the Diplomatic mission of the Ukrainian People's Republic in Rome and its subsections — the Ukrainian Press-Bureau, under the cover of which Ukrainian published word, information about Ukraine was created and spread, was caused by the demolition in 1917 of «the prison of nations», as the Russian Empire was called in civilized Western world, and by the emersion of the Ukrainian People's Republic in south-western precincts of this empire.

When at the beginning of 1919 there arose a real threat of surrendering Kyiv to Bolshevik troops, sent from Moscow, the government of the UPR Directoire takes a decision to forward urgently several diplomatic missions extraordinary to the West. The principal task of such missions was to inform the leaders of the Entente countries about the situation in Ukraine and to demand the recognition of the Ukrainian People's Republic as a sovereign independent country.

It was also supposed that highly-educated Ukrainian delegation would soon organize abroad the publishing of different editions mainly of informative, propagandistic and educational character. As it is known, such missions set off to Great Britain, the United States of America, Greece, Belgium, Denmark, the Vatican and Italy.

To Rome the UPR mission, headed by Dmytro Antonovych, set off in January of the same year.

Dmytro Antonovych was a renowned person in political and diplomatic circles; the son of well-known historian Volodymyr Antonovych, ex-minister of naval ways in the governments, headed by Volodymyr Vynnychenko and Vsevolod Golubovych, one of the founders of the Revolutionary Ukrainian Party (RUP), prominent activist of the Ukrainian Social-Democratic Party.

Just he was the person Kyiv set great hopes on concerning diplomatic relations of Italy with the Ukrainian People's Republic. But yet in the halfway the mission receives an unexpectedly inimical telegram: the Italian government informed that Antonovych's coming to Rome was undesirable [1, p. 6].

The reality was like that: Ukraine as a sovereign independent state had no place on the political map of Europe, as Italian government saw it.

Obviously, having scanty information on the history of Ukrainian people, the majority of Italian authorities and politicians had no sympathy with Ukraine and no intention to solve the Ukrainian question positively. But the Vatican adhered to more restraint sagacious position. The then Pope Benedict XV, having acknowledged the Ukrainian People's Republic, sent a salutary telegram to Symon Petliura. In a separate letter, dated February, 21, 1921 he addressed metropolitan Andrii Sheptytskyi, saying:

«Just because in our heart we have a hope on the returning of peoples of the East to common Christian faith, hope deeply, that through Ukrainians, tightly linked with St. Peter's Chair... very soon the expectations of our prominent predecessor Urban VIII, who said well-known words: «I hope, that through you, my Russins, the East will return...» will come true.» [2, p. 79]. The Pope received M. Tyshkevych, accredited the ambassador of the Ukrainian People's Republic at the Apostolic See and, in return, sent the plenipotentiary of the Vatican padre Jenakki to Ukraine.

These were the conditions under which the mission of the UPR, the members of which managed to getto Rome, had to start their activities.

The first step of the mission was the foundation of the Ukrainian Press-Bureau, which officially started its work on the 1st of June. It was located not far from the center of the Italian capital, its address was: 163, Torino str., the 5th floor. According to the personnel list the staff numbered 7 members. Among them Ukrainians-journalists Vsevolod Shebediev, Taisia Lupovetska-Balmen, Ivan Hrynenko, Italians-journalists Antonia Pescarzolli, typists Sendrini, Bettarini, courier El Piccollo.

At the beginning of October, 1919, with the aim of reviving the Press-Bureau activities, the head of the mission Dmytro Antonovych invited for cooperation Yevhen Onatskyi who knew Italian perfectly well.

The latter came to Italy on October, 6, after involuntary staying in Switzerland for several months as a result of staff reduction in UPR diplomatic missions abroad. Soon he will become the director of this bureau, then a secretary, and «since June, 1920 — the attache and, in fact, the head of the mission, up to the end of its activities in 1922» [3].

Notwithstanding his young age (Yevhen was only 25 at that time), a new co-worker came into contact with others very soon, fully showed his creative and managerial abilities. Some time later the diaries and notebooks of this outstanding Ukrainian journalist, who had the talent to neatly and exactly characterize an interlocutor, were published in the West. And that is why today we have the possibility to reproduce the appearance and images of those, who, with the help of a printed word, defended abroad the honor and dignity of the young Ukrainian People's Republic, which were practically trampled down with the boots of invaders from the North. Extracts of such characteristics are cited from the book of memories «Along sloping surface: Notes of Journalist and Diplomat», which was published in 1964 by Munich publishing house "Dniprova Khvyliya" [4].

Vsevolod Shebediev: «Tall, stout, with a small goatish beard, with a face, dugged all over with deep furrows, no matter that in the blossom of youth. In his unusual face there was something of both: a faun and a person, used to thinking. A real type of a bohemian journalist, very attractive still.» [4, p. 22–23].

Taisiia Lypovetska-Balmen: «Blond, beautiful, slender and graceful as a poplar. Very young still... Having left native Volyn for abroad, she «jumped» to marriage with some Englishman, being different in both temper and intellectual interests. Had to divorce, leaving, with the pain in her heart, the only child... Makes impression of a very able, talented person.» [4, p. 23].

Doctor Ivan Hrynenko: «A man of strong stature, round-headed, with stubborn resolute jaw and with one shoulder, always higher than the other... Everything shows he is a person highly impulsive and hot-tempered, with still burning ambitions. Having become an emigrant, he did not waste time, but entered Pisa university, which he graduated with a doctoral degree in Agronomics. Married, has a son, a little boy. Comes from Nizhyn.» [4, p. 24].

Antonio Pescarzoli: «One of interesting personalities who could be met. A kind of volcano of eloquence and intellectual improvisation. Witticism, paradox thoughts are born in his head every minute and every minute they must be embodied into a chain of refined phrases. His main task is — polemic articles in «La Voce del' Ucraina» and in the Italian press for the defense of Ukraine. He is especially fond of polemics with Prince Volkonskyi and other Russian «bisons» remnants of Black-Hundred «indivisibility» [4, p. 24].

Typist Sandrini: «Types with extraordinary speed — he is a phenomenon... A lively person, excitable» [4, p. 25].

Typist Bettarini: «Types slower, but knows French, from which, if needed translates into Italian. A walking grief. He seems to have problems in the family...» [4, p. 25].

Summing up such vivid, brisk characteristics we can see the staff, different in characters, age, life experience. But what united them was high professionalism, exceptional intellect, and, what is more important, — their longing for full employment of all possible means, including their principal weapon — the truth about Ukraine and Ukrainians.

There were a lot of obstacles in such activities. About insurmountable difficulties, which the Ukrainian mission had to overcome from the very start of its coming to Rome we can also find information in Onatskyi's diaries. For example, such an extract: «The main problem is the absence of truthful news. Telegraph agency would be of great help. The primary source of our information — Vienna weekly «Volia» (The Freedom), but with delay. And various mass media bring different news about Kyiv and Petliura — and we did not know which of it was true. But still we constantly sent our news to Italian mass media in histotrophicbulletins.» [4, p. 52].

In fact, under conditions, when the government of the Ukrainian People's Republic broke on the wheel (after Kyiv, the capitals of the UPR were Fastiv, Vinnytsia, Ternopil, Pidvolochynsk and, finally, Kamianets-Podilskyi), when the reliable connection among governmental institutions was so poor, that it was difficult, almost impossible, to verify the truthfulness of information got from different newspapers.

Principal directions and results of the activities

Not numerous group of the Ukrainian diplomatic mission experienced a large massif of antiukrainian propaganda which, as a powerful torrent, was directed through Russian and Polish embassies and their numerous missions to all the countries of Europe, including Italy. One can understand, that in such information flow the Ukrainian movement was treated as only a subkind of Bolsheviks movement, having certain «independence-oriented» elements. As the one, which does not deserve the least compassion and must undergo strict repression. The more valuable are painful efforts of a handful of Ukrainians who, in such situation, stood up for their own beliefs on behalf of millions of their compatriots.

Let's give some more valuable evidence of an immediate copartner of Ukrainian publishing group in Italy, who was little known in his Motherland.

«I have the responsibility to analyze some 20 Italian periodicals and some French ones and draw out from them everything, that concerns Ukraine and needs this or that reaction.» [4, p. 22].

«The work for Press-Bureau is extremely important and responsible — it goes about the struggle for the existence of our state, its political and national independence.» [4, p. 29].

«The weapon of our struggle against the enemies of the Ukrainian independence in Italy had to be our weekly «La Voce del' Ucraina» (Holos Ukrainy). But it comes out too irregularly... Unfortunately, the articles were handed in anonymous — and now it gives no possibility to clear out, which article belongs to whom... More than that, large pages look without authors' names as a howling wilderness without a bush or a tree. Nevertheless, the weekly content was always at the highest level.» [4, p. 42].

The weekly «La Voce del' Ucraina», the publication of the Diplomatic mission of the UPR, was issued in Italian in Pome on 1919-1920. The format was

A3, bulk — 4–8 columns. The editor was the well-known civil and political activist of Central Rada in Kyiv, journalist Myhailo Yeremiiv. Among the newspaper creators there were Ukrainians Yevhen Onatskyi, Ivan Hrunenko, Vsevolod Shebediev, Taisiia Lypovetska-Balmen. Italians also helped to publish newspaper journalist Antonio Pescalocci, typists Sandrini, Bettarini, language editor and courier El Piccolo. Editorial office was located in the Ukrainian Press-Bureau, not far from the center of Rome, its address was: 163, Torino str., the 5th floor.

The first issue came out on June, 9, 1919. Since Italian government did not acknowledge the Ukrainian People's Republic officially, from the very beginning the publishers faced financial and organizational problems.

They failed to keep to the announced weekly issue. In 1919 only 15 issues came out, in 1920 — 35 issues. The unique newspaper file on this periodical is saved in the library of Ukrainian Papal Collegium in Rome.

The editorial policy had its own peculiarities. If the materials for «Bulletin of the Ukrainian Press-Bureau in Rome» (published two-three times a week in a cyclostyle way) were mainly of information character, «La Voce del' Ucraina» (published in a relief printing way) was founded as an analytical publication of Diplomatic mission.

The principal task of this unique Italian language newspaper of Ukrainians in Rome was to give multifaceted and truthful analytical information about Ukraine and Ukrainian inspirations to Italian authorities' political institutions and mass media. The accent was made on two topics:

- explanation of the grounds for the objectivity of the Ukrainian state existence;
- polemics with Russian publications, which denied such objectivity.

In 1920 the range of publications was widened — to history, politics, economics, they added literature, the arts, church and so on.

Content analysis of periodicals shows one peculiar thing: failing in efficiency the editorial staff won with receiving positive characteristics of their publications. Among them there were — truly well-thought problem-thematic palette of issues, standfast keeping to balance in publishing materials of different genres — from information notes to analytical articles. For the latter the high level of persuasiveness and publicity character were most peculiar.

In this context it is worth giving an extract from the article of A. Pescartoli, mentioned above Italian journalist, coworker of the weekly, whose polemic articles against permanent Ukraine-phobia attacks of Russian emigrants must always get, according to Ye. Onatskyi, approving comments of Italian well-wishers and sympathizes with the UPR. It goes about deflating of endless Ukraine-hating paragraphs to Italian newspaper «Il Popolo Romano» written by wrongheaded Vladimir Frenkel: «German Vladimir Frenkel has got a tremendous trouble — the existence of the Ukrainian People's Republic. The Ukrainians dared to proclaim their «independence» not asking

for the permission from him, great Frenkel, glorious author of foolish dialogues on Russian revolution. It is unprecedented! Where shall we end with such disrespect to such authorities! Frenkel doesn't sleep, doesn't digest, doesn't understand anything at all. He sees only red, red, red. Slow-written (blunt, stupid) revolutionary, alumnus of tsarist «horodovyh» (policemen), unsuccessful writer, cloudy brain, Frenkel wastes his days in writing cannibal (man-eating) and illiteralantiukrainian lampoons. And then, incredibly impudent, offers them to periodicals!» [4, p. 44].

Issue 11 attracts reader's attention by well-grounded V. Shebediev's articles «Volodymyr Korolenko and Ukrainian Independence», «Volition of Ukrainian people» and I. Hrynenko's «The importance of Ukrainian ports» and «The development of the idea of politicalnationality in Ukraine». Editorial truculent article as a reply on the Russian ex-sergeant's publication «Reminiscences about Ukraine in pro-Russian journal «Don Quixote» («Don Kihot»)»; Ukrainian women's appeal to the global world as to Moscow enslavement of Ukraine, Memorandum of Ukrainian Red Cross concerning Ukrainian captives in Poland; Independent Ukrainian Socialists Ultimatum to Bolshevists; V. Vynnychenko's biography with his portrait; necrology of F. Matyshevskyi and so on. A number of publications from Ukrainian Italian-language newsletter «La Voce del' Ucraina» were republished by popular Italian newspapers. On December, 8 «Il Popolo Romano» published (with the reference to the first printing) the article about epidemic diseases in Ukraine, prompted by ruin and civil war. Milan «Il Sekollo» reprinted the reference of the Ukrainian government about the situation in Halychyna signed by Issak Mazepa.

At the same time this newspaper publishes its own material about Ukraine under the rubric heading «The results of the fallacious Entente» — «Ukraine will be new Poland: inequitable partition».

The publications of this periodical, in which the authors, earnestly, with advanced arguments and publicists' inspiration stood up for honor and dignity of the people, who had been fighting for the right to live by their own laws in their own home, haven't lost their topicality even now. The best ones of these publications are worthy of being included into the readers and other educational suppliers for future journalists and editors-publishers.

Highly appreciating the range of problems and topics, discussed in «La Voce del' Ucraina», one of active founders of Ukrainian journalism in a foreign land Ye. Onatskyi called this weekly «the instrument of our fighting in Italy against enemies of Ukrainian independence».

In the library-archives of the Chief Council of the rank of saint Basil the Great, which is situated in Via San Giosafat, 8, the author of this publication managed to find a short reference about tasks, ways of their attaining and results of the activities of this very special publishing subunit, little-known in our historyyet. This anonymous document, which consists of only two

typed pages on thin, so-called cigarette, paper is entitled «The review of Ukrainian Press-Bureau activities in Rome since July, 1, 1919 till March, 1920» [5]. The content of this reference shows, that Press-Bureau had to solve two tasks:

a) to give versatile and truthful information about Ukraine and Ukrainian claims to Italian state and political institutions, the press, the public;

b) to collect and report information obtained from foreign sources to Ukrainian government and its foreign missions.

It is clear, that most attention was paid to the first task. The work was being done in several directions.

The first one: «The Bulletins of Ukrainian Press-Bureau in Rome» were published with means of small-scale polygraph (so-called hectographs). The language of the periodical — Italian. Planned periodicity — 2–3 times per week, volume of each issue — 2–4 pages, pressrun — 100–300 copies. Factual materials for bulletins were taken from newspapers, published in Ukraine and Europe. From Italian, some French, Belgian newspapers and journals the editors picked out everything, where Ukraine and Ukrainian problems were at least mentioned, and what became the object of comments from the Ukrainian point of view. The emphasis was placed on two topics — the grounds of the objectivity of Ukrainian state existence and polemics with Russian publications, which denied such objectivity. 56 issues of «Bulletin» were published during first nine months.

The second one. Simultaneously with bulletin issues, the materials of which were mainly of information character, since June, 9 the periodical «La voce del' Ucraina» began to be published, analytical articles of well-known Ukrainian and foreign authors were its indisputable trump. The volume of the periodical — from 4 pages and more. The language was Italian. Planned periodicity — weekly. The range of topics was substantially extended — history, economics, politics, literature, the arts, religion, etc.

The third one. Publication of articles on burning Ukrainian problems in key Italian periodicals. For example, the publication of the letter of the Cossack chieftain (the Chief otaman) S. Petliura to a well-known politician Pelisie the day before the elections in Italy had got wide publicity. This was a repartee (acute answer) to widely advertised rude attacks of Russian emigration press against one of the prominent of that time leaders of Ukrainian nation. Popular «Carriered' Italia», preparing a special pre-election issue, published three pieces of information about Ukraine, written by Ukrainian Press-Bureau in Rome. «Selecting these two articles about Ukrainian concerns and Petliura's letter for its election-devoted issue this all-Italian daily paper as if imposed the duty to defend Ukrainian people on will-be deputies of this party» [16, p. 2]. In general, as it is written in the notice about Bureau activity, almost every Italian periodical published this or that news from Ukrainian Press-Bureau.

The fourth one. Arrangement of lectures on Ukrainian history, politics, culture, the arts, literature in Press-Bureau. There existed a list of permanent guests — journalists, politicians, scientists, Italian public representatives. There were held six evening meetings. «All the lectures had full house and were great success» [5, p. 2].

The fifth one. Publishing and distributing of stitched booklets on social-political problems and books of Ukrainian classic authors in Italian. From all the branches of Press-Bureau activities this one proved to be the least effective. Only one stitched booklet was published — «L Ukrainadananciella Konferencadella pare». Though there were two more manuscripts — translations of two books, notable for Ukrainians — «The History of Ukraine by Mykhailo Hrushevskyi and «Kobzar» by Taras Shevchenko, the Press-Bureau failed to publish them because of lack of finance.

Truth to tell, one of the most important Ukrainian publishing projects was realized in Rome, but after the Diplomatic mission stopped its activities in Rome. It goes about the first translation of Shevchenko's «Kobzar» into Italian, accomplished by well-known cultural activist and writer Mlada Lypovetska together with Italian philologist Caesar Meano. The presentation of this book to Italian public took place in a special way — through the concert of Ukrainian songs to words from Ukrainian prophet. Pieces of poetry were recited by translators themselves and by Italian engineer Negri, songs were sung by Mlada Lypovetska.

Giving honor to this outstanding event Yevhen Onatskyi will write in his diary: «Translation of «Kobzar» into Italian has been prepared for a long time — since the time of our Diplomatic mission and Press-Bureau in 1919. That is why, let us hope, it will justify such a long preparatory work, which has been done in such inauspicious situation, and will do a great favor to Ukrainian concerns, submitting the pearls of our national poetry to European readers».

Sent to Rome by the government of UPR in the dramatic period of its existence, a narrow circle of Ukrainians honestly and efficiently did their work aimed at assertion of the idea of Ukrainian statehood. This idea was realized only in 1991 [7].

Conclusions

The activities of the Ukrainian Press-Bureau of UPR Diplomatic mission in Rome is understudied and underestimated.

It began its activities at the end of 1919 in the situation when new Ukrainian authorities were not acknowledged by Italian government. It stopped its activities in 1922. The editorial staff, headed by Yevhen Onatskyi since June, 1920, numbered 7 coworkers. The task of the Press-Bureau was to inform the authorities of the Entente countries about the situation in Ukraine and to claim for recognition of the UPR as a sovereign independent country.

The most important results of publishing activities of the Bureau are:

1. Publishing by cyclo-stylish method of «Bulletin of the Ukrainian Press-Bureau in Rome» (information periodical, issued 2–3 times per week in Italian, volume – 2–4 pages, pressrun – 100–300 copies; 56 issues are preserved).
2. Publishing of analytical periodical «La Voce del' Ucraina» (intended as a weekly in Italian, 50 issues were published).
3. Writing publications for Italian press by the Bureau staff.
4. Arrangement of lectures on Ukrainian issues for Italian public.
5. Publishing and distributing booklets on social-political problems and books of Ukrainian classics, translated into Italian.

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УКРАЇНСЬКЕ ПРЕСОВЕ БЮРО ДИПЛОМАТИЧНОЇ МІСІЇ УКРАЇНСЬКОЇ НАРОДНОЇ РЕСПУБЛІКИ У РИМІ ЯК УРОК ДЛЯ СУЧАСНОЇ НАЦІОНАЛЬНОЇ ЖУРНАЛІСТИКИ

Микола Тимошик,

д-р філол. н, проф.

Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв,

вул. Є. Коновальця, 36, 01601, Київ, Україна

e-mail: nkin@ukr.net

ORCID ID 0000-0002-7011-3022

Стаття написана на основі опрацьованих автором бібліотечних та архівних колекцій української еміграції в Римі під час наукового стажування в Італії. Уперше висвітлюється маловідома сторінка українсько-італійських відносин під кутом зору постання, організації праці та результатів діяльності Українського пресового бюро Дипломатичної місії УНР у Римі 1919–1920 років.

Як відомо, від початків утворення Української Народної Республіки дипломатичні представництва з Києва були вислані до кількох впливових країн Західної Європи. Їхнім головним завданням було широко інформувати керівників країн Антанти щодо ситуації в Україні та домагатися від цих країн визнання Української Народної Республіки як суверенної незалежної держави. У питаннях розв'язання російсько-української проблеми цей уряд дотримувався на той час проросійської позиції.

З огляду на те, що уряд Італії не визнав Україну як самостійну державу, дипломатична місія УНР не мала офіційного статусу і фактично працювала в Римі в напівлегальних умовах. Місію очолював син відомого українського історика Дмитро Антонович.

Подаються характеристики штатних працівників місії — Всеволода Шебедева, Таїсії Липовецької-Бальмен, Івана Гриненка, Антоніо Пескалоцці, друкарів-машиністів, італійців за походженням, Сандріні та Беттанірі.

Детально аналізується пресова діяльність місії і зокрема керівника прес-бюро Євгена Онацького. Проаналізована редакційна політика «Бюлетеню Українського пресового бюро в Римі» та тижневика італійською мовою «La Voce del' Ucraina».

У висновках наголошується на найголовніших результатах пресової та видавничої діяльності цього бюро. А вони були такі:

- випуск циклостильовим способом «Бюлетені Українського пресового бюро в Римі» (інформаційне видання, що виходив двічі-тричі на тиждень італійською мовою обсягом від двох до чотирьох сторінок, накладом від 100 до 300 примірників; збережено 56 чисел цього видання);

- випуск аналітичного періодичного видання «Голос України» (за задумом, тижневик італійською мовою, вийшло у світ 50 чисел);

- підготовка працівниками бюро публікацій для італійської преси;

- проведення для італійської громадськості лекцій на українознавчі теми;

- видання й поширення в перекладенні італійською мовою брошур на суспільно-політичну тематику та книг класиків української літератури.

Ключові слова: Україна, Італія, пресове бюро, дипломатична місія УНР, Дмитро Антонович, Євген Онацький, бюлетень, газета «La Voce del' Ucraina», українсько-італійські відносини, італійська преса, українське питання в Європі.